

PID4NFDI Communication Strategy

Version 1.0

PID4NFDI

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Imprint

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About

PID4NFDI is the basic service for persistent identifiers in development for the German National Research Data Infrastructure ([Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur – NFDI](#)). PID4NFDI is part of and funded through [Base4NFDI](#).

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¹ Proposal for the initialization phase of PID4NFDI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14281250>

Abstract

This is the communication strategy of PID4NFDI, the basic service in development for persistent identifiers (PIDs) for the German National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur – NFDI). In order to support PID4NFDI in its central objective of consolidating and evolving the PID service landscape within NFDI at all levels – including in terms of communication – the communication strategy primarily defines the following important aspects (and is structured accordingly): objectives and measures, target audience (stakeholders), and the respective communication channels. The communication strategy is a product (deliverable) of PID4NFDI’s initialization phase and addresses the time beyond, currently the two-year integration phase.

Version History

1.0 Creation and initial publication.

Abbreviations

DFG	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (German Research Foundation)
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DMP	data management plan
ELN	electronic lab notebook
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	findability, accessibility, interoperability, reusability (FAIR principles)
ID	identifier
NFDI	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (German National Research Data Infrastructure)
PID	persistent identifier
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	research data management
SWOT	Strength, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats

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Introduction

PID4NFDI is the basic service for persistent identifiers (PIDs) in development for the German National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur – NFDI).² It is part of and funded through Base4NFDI, a joint initiative of all 26 NFDI consortia to foster and establish reliable NFDI-wide basic services.

PIDs are central for research data management (RDM) to fulfill the principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (FAIR). However, various disciplines and resources result in diverse requirements and different levels of maturity in PID implementation in NFDI consortia. PID4NFDI designs a work program to build an NFDI basic service on established PID infrastructures. As there already is a mature and globally used PID provider landscape and PID needs are highly individual in the consortia, PID4NFDI's intended services are defined as a set of several components that are tailored to the needs of NFDI stakeholders. PID4NFDI aims to enhance the usability of existing PID systems for NFDI by supporting improvements in technical and organizational interoperability, boosting metadata quality, and creating awareness through training and outreach programs. In essence, the central objective of PID4NFDI is to consolidate and evolve the PID service landscape within NFDI at all levels: technical, organizational, methodological, and in communication.

PID4NFDI's first service development phase, the one-year initialization phase from January to December 2024,³ focused on use cases and requirements analyses, concept development, stakeholder identification, and setting up outreach channels. Outcomes are a NFDI-wide PID landscape analysis,⁴ several use case analyses,⁵ a concept for training resources,⁶ a PID governance concept,⁷ and a stakeholder workshop,⁸ among others.

² Further information and resources are available on PID4NFDI's website: pid.services.base4nfdi.de

³ Roland Bertelmann et al. (2024). PID4NFDI – Persistent Identifier Services for the German National Research Data Infrastructure: Proposal for the Initialisation Phase of Base4NFDI. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14281250>

⁴ Sara El-Gebali et al. (2024). Landscape of PID practices within NFDI services.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14277479>

⁵ Use case analyses: StrainInfo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14357800>), FAIRagro (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14506202>), KonsortSWD (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14327770>), Text+ (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14327691>)

⁶ Torsten Kahlert, Stephanie Hagemann-Wilholt (2024). PID4NFDI Training Concept.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14267399>

⁷ Stephanie Hagemann-Wilholt, Torsten Kahlert (2024). Concept for Sustainable PID Registration Workflows. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14267446>

⁸ PID4NFDI (2024). PID4NFDI Stakeholder Workshop. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14267399>

In the second phase, the two-year integration phase from January 2025 to December 2026,⁹ PID4NFDI aims to enhance PID integration within NFDI consortia, considering varying provider maturity levels and community adoption. It will focus on integrating PIDs throughout the research data lifecycle, using data management plans (DMPs) and electronic lab notebooks (ELNs) as pilot implementations. Special emphasis will be placed on the integration of PIDs for objects for which PID registration is still emerging, such as research instruments, material samples, highly granular data, as well as projects and awards. The goal is to boost the impact of PIDs by improving metadata quality and interoperability through technical, organizational, and strategic measures. Furthermore, governance guidelines, outreach efforts, and a modular training concept will promote PID awareness and adoption across disciplines. This approach will be prototyped collaboratively with NFDI consortia partners, ensuring broad applicability. Interoperability, metadata, governance, training and support, and community engagement components will together form the *PID Coordination Hub*, a central entry point for users of the PID4NFDI service portfolio.

To reach its goals, PID4NFDI must have a good strategy for communication, especially as communication and outreach are central objectives. The communication strategy primarily defines the following important aspects, and is structured accordingly: objectives and measures, target audience (stakeholders), and the respective communication channels. The communication strategy is a product (deliverable) of the initialization phase and addresses the time beyond, currently the two-year integration phase.

Objectives and Measures

One central objective of PID4NFDI is to consolidate and evolve the PID service landscape within NFDI at all levels. Due to the decentralized structure of the NFDI, stakeholder-oriented communication is one of the most crucial tools for achieving the initiative's goals. By actively engaging diverse stakeholders, addressing their specific needs, and fostering clear and transparent dialogue, communication efforts can align priorities, build trust, and enhance collaboration across the network. It is relevant for promoting the understanding of the importance of PIDs

⁹ Sven Bingert et al. (2024). Persistent Identifier Services for the German National Research Data Infrastructure: Proposal for the Integration Phase of Base4NFDI.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14281255>

in the research data infrastructure and integrating that in NFDI's structures by increasing awareness and adoption of PIDs through training, outreach and community engagement.¹⁰ Adequate communication is also important to raise awareness for PID4NFDI itself within the NFDI community in order to make its services and results visible and encourage broad and active participation of NFDI consortia in its progress and tasks. Another objective is to ensure that the activities of PID4NFDI are complementary to other national and international endeavours. In line with the outreach efforts, good communication will increase project impact, better involve stakeholders, and foster collaborations.

Cornerstones must therefore be the identification of relevant stakeholders within and beyond NFDI (see *Target Audience – Stakeholders*) to establish, maintain and consolidate contact and exchange with these stakeholders through the right approaches and channels (see *Objectives and Measures* and *Communication Channels*), as well as to promote exchange and networking among them (where PID4NFDI can act as a multiplier and liaison partner). In order to communicate appropriately, target group-specific messages must be considered and the right tonality and communication style be present. To successfully communicate the importance of PID4NFDI to the NFDI community, good integration with NFDI's structure and organization is important, which requires coordination with other NFDI basic services as well as consortia and sections, and consideration of the NFDI-wide communication strategy.

The range of PID4NFDI's communication measures is manifold and is largely determined by the target audience, the stakeholders (see *Target Audience – Stakeholders*), the available channels for communication (see *Communication Channels*), and the proposal and work schedule for the integration phase, which covers a broad range of communicative approaches, from knowledge and training resources to information on outreach events and community engagement activities – all accumulated into the upcoming PID Coordination Hub (see *Website and PID Coordination Hub*). The measures are intended to induce reaching and actively involving the identified stakeholders.

PID4NFDI will complement these activities and outcomes with its outreach engagement: engaging with the community online (see *Newsletter and Mailing Lists, Online Fora, and Social Media*) and in-person by attending and contributing

¹⁰ In 2022, a perceived gap regarding PIDs resulted in the creation of the Persistent Identifier Services Working Group in the NFDI section Common Infrastructures (which later led to the initiative for PID4NFDI). A subsequent SWOT analysis carried out by the working group in 2023 showed that tailored communication regarding PIDs for NFDI is lacking; see the proposal for PID4NFDI's initialization phase (footnote 3).

to various events (see *Events*), as well as through different forms of publications (see *Publications*).

For successful communication in terms of PID4NFDI's goals, it is helpful to select and reiterate core messages on the importance of PIDs in RDM as well as PID4NFDI's support and service agenda on a case-by-case basis, for example:

- PIDs are essential for FAIR research data.
- A working PID infrastructure requires sustainable PID systems and governance.
- Improvements in technical and organizational interoperability are important in strengthening the usefulness of PIDs.
- PID4NFDI builds on proven infrastructures and takes into account the specific requirements of the NFDI community.
- PID4NFDI develops a NFDI-wide strategy for persistent identifiers.

Monitoring the success of the communication and a reevaluation of the communication strategy is important. This could include, but is not limited to, monitoring and qualitative tracking of the NFDI consortia actively involved in PID4NFDI's activities, feedback surveys on satisfaction and knowledge growth of the stakeholders, measurement of participant numbers at events and training courses, and tracking access and use statistics of resources and outputs.

Target Audience – Stakeholders

This section identifies PID4NFDI's target audience – the relevant stakeholders from within NFDI and beyond – in order to reach out to them, involve them in activities, and bring them together. The stakeholders' positions and roles may be diverse, reaching from researchers, data stewards, or repository managers at research organizations to staff at infrastructure services providers and decision-makers in funding institutions. Notably, stakeholders do not just include individuals, but also entire consortia, working groups, informal initiatives, and other superordinate organized units or structures. PID4NFDI continuously identifies relevant stakeholders, both in NFDI and beyond, and documents its meetings and exchanges with them.

Stakeholders Within NFDI

Within NFDI, the primary stakeholders for PID4NFDI are the 26 domain-specific **NFDI consortia**, with all their different members of various roles, backgrounds and from various types of organizations. Important individuals from the consortia are the ones working with PID implementation, either technically or on infrastructure or governance level, e. g. repository managers or information officers. Some consortia have formed support structures of specific interest for PID4NFDI, the RDM helpdesks¹¹.

The use and integration of PIDs is evident within the consortia, but it varies widely across different use cases, with diverse levels of maturity and reliance on a range of PID providers. These differences reflect the varying needs, priorities, and resources of the communities involved, highlighting the importance of coordinated efforts to harmonize practices and ensure consistency across the NFDI. Typically, these are specific use cases that will require special attention by PID4NFDI. There are already involved efforts from several consortia since the initialization phase (participation in use case analyses and workshops as well as giving feedback on developed resources and solutions), and more to follow in the integration phase (collaboration with additional use cases and participation in focus groups and further workshops). Among them are use cases from the following consortia: KonsortSWD, DAPHNE4NFDI, FAIRagro, NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Objects, NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Earth, NFDI4Cat, NFDI4Microbiota, Text+. With others, there is also already established contact with PID4NFDI, which needs to be strengthened. With some consortia, there is of yet little to no interaction, which needs to be addressed. In the integration phase, several activities of engaging stakeholders from the consortia are planned, e. g. research data lifecycle-orientated focus groups and workshops (WP1 – T1.1) and community engagement and facilitation of outreach events with PID liaisons and stakeholders within consortia (WP5 – T5.3).

The current five **NFDI sections**, including their working groups, address cross-cutting topics relevant to multiple or all consortia. They collaborate closely with Base4NFDI, the joint initiative of all discipline-specific consortia, to develop basic services. Involved are members from NFDI consortia and Base4NFDI, from the broader scientific community, and from industry partners. PID4NFDI is in contact with three of the five sections: *(Meta)data*, *Terminologies*, *Provenance*; *Training &*

¹¹ See the [list of existing RDM helpdesks of NFDI consortia](#).

Education; and *Common Infrastructures*; the latter having initiated the establishment of PID4NFDI and comprising a working group on PID services.

PID4NFDI is part of **Base4NFDI**, which is an important stakeholder – as are the seven **other basic services currently in development**. PID4NFDI is in sustained contact with both Base4NFDI and the other basic services through monthly meetings as well as events organized by Base4NFDI. PID4NFDI is supported through Base4NFDI also by dedicated service stewards who facilitate collaboration between consortia and sections and by members of its task areas. PID4NFDI will strengthen more direct communication and exchange with other basic services in development, especially those which have vested interests in PID management and systems. Two basic services in development, DMP4NFDI and IAM4NFDI, supported PID4NFDI's integration phase proposal.

Other stakeholders in the NFDI for PID4NFDI to take into consideration are the current projects **Data Literacy in NFDI** and **FAIR Data Spaces**.

Stakeholders Beyond NFDI

Actors in the context of PIDs and RDM beyond NFDI are also important for PID4NFDI as another important group of stakeholders.

PID service providers are crucial stakeholders for projects on persistent identifiers because they manage and maintain the infrastructure for assigning and resolving PIDs, establish standards and best practices for PID usage, thereby contributing to interoperability and consistency across different systems. Important for PID4NFDI are the services of the two project partners **DataCite** and **GWDG** (with **ePIC**, the European Persistent Identifier Consortium), as well as further service providers such as the **ARK Alliance**, **Crossref**, **ORCID**, and **ROR** (Research Organization Registry), among others.

The **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)** is important to recognize as a stakeholder itself and as an environment of and for stakeholders. This is especially relevant as the NFDI seeks to become an EOSC national node and in light of EOSC's PID policy¹², which defines expectations and requirements for PIDs and PID implementation to support a functioning environment of FAIR research for EOSC. Relevant actors are some of the **EOSC working groups** (EOSC FAIR Working Group and EOSC Architecture Working Group, which have authored EOSC's PID policy), the

¹² EOSC Executive Board (ed.) (2020). A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud. Report from the European Open Science Cloud FAIR and Architecture Working Groups. European Commission. <https://doi.org/10.2777/926037>

FAIR-IMPACT¹³ and **FAIRCORE4EOSC** projects (both focused on enhancing FAIR principles, including PID solutions, within the EOSC ecosystem), the **EOSC Task Force on PID Policy and Implementation**, and the **EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Group OA1 on PIDs** (which continues the work of the former EOSC-A Task Force on PIDs). PID4NFDI is in communication with some of these actors, either directly or by proxy through its partners: FAIR-IMPACT includes DataCite as one of its partners; GWDG and DataCite are receiving funding by FAIRCORE4EOSC and are developing crucial EOSC core components in this context; the EOSC Task Force on PID Policy and Implementation is supported by TIB, GWDG, and DataCite.

The proposal and work schedule for the integration phase of PID4NFDI takes up some of these EOSC relations: The PID guidelines to be developed for NFDI (WP1 – T1.3/D1.2), to be based on the PID roadmap of PID Network Germany, will also consider the EOSC PID policy. Outcomes of FAIRCORE4EOSC, among them an evaluation tool for PID provider compliance with specific policies, will be evaluated and adapted to be incorporated into the PID4NFDI's PID Coordination Hub (WP1 – T1.4/D1.3). Also, the efforts for community engagement and facilitation of outreach events (WP5 – T5.3) will be aligned with both PID Network Germany and the EOSC framework.

There are multiple **other projects and initiatives** important in the domain of PIDs and PID implementation. Among them are: **Research Data Alliance** (RDA; e. g. the **Persistent Identification of Instruments Working Group** and **National PID Strategies Interest Group**), national PID initiatives (e. g., in the USA, in the UK and in Ireland), **JISC's PID initiative**, **Project FREYA**, **MoreBrains**, **Africa PID Alliance**, **Australian Research Data Commons**, **PID Forum Finland**.

PID4NFDI closely collaborates with the DFG-funded project **PID Network Germany**, which aims to establish a network in science and culture that promotes and consolidates the application, implementation, standardization and international connectivity of PID systems on a national and international level. The projects are aligned through bilateral coordination and a well-established exchange of information between them, which is important due to the different scopes: PID4NFDI focuses on PID implementation in the context of NFDI and especially within NFDI consortia with analyses of specific use cases, while PID Network Germany addresses the wider scientific and cultural sector, covering a more extensive range of PID application areas beyond research data (management) and

¹³ The FAIR-IMPACT project has developed guidelines for creating EOSC-compliant PID policies, see: René Horik, Wim Hugo (2024). Guidelines for creating a user tailored EOSC Compliant PID Policy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14092489>

without in-depth evaluations of use cases. PID4NFDI can use and integrate results and findings from PID Network Germany, and vice versa. In the integration phase, PID4NFDI will develop NFDI-wide PID guidelines in coordination with PID Network Germany and align them with its national PID roadmap in development (WP1 – T1.3/D1.2). PID4NFDI will also collaborate with PID Network Germany to ensure that NFDI and the German scientific infrastructure are connected to international initiatives, such as the EOSC, by aligning efforts and activities regarding the EOSC framework (WP5 – T5.3).

Communication Channels

For effective outreach, the appropriate selection of communication channels in alignment with communication goals, identified target groups and suitable content is crucial. The strategy of PID4NFDI here is twofold: Reuse and strengthen existing, well-received channels, fora, and networks; and open up new communication channels in case of distinct gaps and carefully considered, stakeholder-oriented needs. Especially to reach out to international – in particular European – PID projects, initiatives and networks, PID4NFDI plans to extensively take advantage of existing channels and networks. Additionally, PID4NFDI embraces direct contacts via individual exchange or communication (e. g., from participating in events) and available channels from the work with stakeholders (e. g., from use case analyses or support consultations with experts from consortia) for its communication. On a technical level, contacting PID4NFDI is currently primarily possible via email and its website as well as via NFDI-internal chat messaging tools, with more options to come (see below).

Website and PID Coordination Hub

During the initialization phase of PID4NFDI, a [website](#) was set up to inform about new developments in the PID landscape, provide information about existing PID standards, and compile resources on best practices. The website also features a news blog, a publications list, and an event calendar to communicate such project-own news and events (or event attendance), as well as project and contact information to get in touch with PID4NFDI.

The integration phase will include a considerable extension of the website: Project activities will be consolidated in a *PID Coordination Hub* for NFDI, providing best

practices, examples, and support for managing PIDs and associated metadata, and thus optimizing standardized approaches across NFDI. This new service for NFDI primarily targets repository managers, infrastructure services providers, and researchers and research organizations implementing or using PID services. Accordingly, the website will become the entry point to the PID Coordination Hub and its communication channels (WP5 – T5.1/M5.1). It will also feature information on outreach events and community engagement activities, with emphasis on use cases and focus groups (see *Events*). A help section will be added with frequently asked questions (WP5 – T5.1/D5.1). Various knowledge, best practice and training resources will be added (WP4 – T4.4/M4.2.). To improve the way of contacting PID4NFDI with PID-specific inquiries, a structured contact form with predefined questions will be added (WP5 – T5.2). The required maintenance of the website will continue, both in terms of technical management and content editing.

Newsletter and Mailing Lists

In terms of email communication, PID4NFDI primarily relies on existing channels such as newsletters (see also *Communication Channels of NFDI and Base4NFDI*) and mailing lists. The most important mailing list is [pid-dialog](#), which is exclusively related to content on PIDs and has around 700 subscribers, is operated by the partner project PID Network Germany, and will be used by PID4NFDI as the primary mailing list. Other related mailing lists (e. g., for matters related to open science and RDM) will be used as well, if appropriate. A pending issue for PID4NFDI is determining if there is the need or demand for a dedicated mailing list for PID-related issues in the context of NFDI (apart from mailing lists of the section Common Infrastructures and its working group on PIDs).

Online Fora

Multiple online fora exist in the broad field of open science and research data. An example dedicated to PIDs is [PID Forum](#), an online forum set up in 2019 for fostering discourse on all matters related to PIDs, featuring a broad range of topics and categories. PID4NFDI will monitor the PID Forum for relevant content and post its own content in an attempt to strengthen its engagement with the platform's community. PID4NFDI will communicate news, events and other project updates in other online fora (e. g., the online foras [of the RDA](#) or [of open-access.network](#)) in case of topical relevance.

Social Media

Communication via social media is a pending issue with the transition into the integration phase. Coordination with Base4NFDI in consideration of its and the NFDI-wide communication strategy is necessary. The current dynamics of social media, controversial developments in social media outlets (such as the occurrences of the platform X, formerly known as Twitter), and the issue of digital sovereignty in science need to be considered and discussed. To test the reach of a social media outlet for PID4NFDI, one possibility could be the use of a decentralized platform such as Mastodon, for which NFDI operates a self-hosted instance (nfdi.social).

Events

After having started with a stakeholder workshop in November 2023 as the first self-hosted event,¹⁴ PID4NFDI will continue to organize different events going forward, primarily as determined by the proposal and work schedule for the integration phase. For outreach and community engagement, problem- or needs-specific workshops will be organized to facilitate exchanges among consortia, PID experts, PID4NFDI staff, and external stakeholders (WP5 – T5.3). Training resources, best practices, use cases, and general topics at the consortia level are going to be presented. The specific topics and formats of these workshops will be determined by the needs and expectations identified in the course of the progress of the integration phase. Furthermore, for the focus groups on research data lifecycles which are to be set up (see *Stakeholders Within NFDI*), workshops will be held to facilitate the focus groups' activities (WP1 – T1.1/M1.1). Events organized by PID4NFDI will be communicated broadly, within and beyond NFDI through the available channels (see *Communication Channels*).

PID4NFDI also attempts to participate in relevant events related to PIDs in RDM. Events in the context of NFDI are prioritized, e. g. NFDI events such as the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI), Base4NFDI events such as the Base4NFDI User Conference, and relevant events of NFDI consortia or sections. National events related to RDM and PIDs are important as well, as they likely allow both exchange within and beyond stakeholders from NFDI in Germany. PID4NFDI regularly attends the events of PID Network Germany for collaboration and

¹⁴ See the report of the stakeholder workshop (footnote 8).

coordination. Wherever possible, PID4NFDI also attends international events related to RDM and PIDs, such as the PIDfest or events of the RDA.

For all events, if PID4NFDI is represented with a contribution, presentations or posters feature a NFDI-compliant design and will typically be made available in a timely manner (see *Publications*).

Publications

Publications and presentation slides of PID4NFDI feature a consistent design and layout ensured by respective templates, compliant with the NFDI corporate design guidelines. Publishing is typically carried out via Zenodo.¹⁵ All publications are [listed on the website](#) (see *Website and PID Coordination Hub*). Open science principles will be followed, with a commitment to making all results publicly available. This will ensure that resources are accessible and usable by stakeholders, encouraging collaboration and enhancing impact within NFDI. In the integration phase, outputs management and curation will be extended (WP5 – T5.4) and encompass all project outputs, such as training materials, outreach resources, and scientific publications.

Communication Channels of NFDI and Base4NFDI

To communicate news, events and other project updates, PID4NFDI also makes use of the existing and available communication channels of NFDI and Base4NFDI. This includes both NFDI's and Base4NFDI's website news and newsletter, the mailing lists of consortia and sections (and their working groups), as well as more informal communication channels, such as the NFDI-internal chat messaging tools.

PID4NFDI will also look out for new communication channels, such as the [NFDI podcast](#) launched in November 2024.

¹⁵ For these publications, PID4NFDI maintains a [Zenodo community](#).